

STRATHE2E TOOL

StrathE2E R package and web-app
for ecosystem modelling

DESCRIPTION

2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
<p>The StrathE2E web-app is an enabling tool to help stakeholders and researcher alike engage with complex computer simulations of marine ecosystems. The open access app allows anyone to choose a geographic region, run a simulation, explore the results and then vary the inputs to create their own experimental scenario. Programmers can also download the StrathE2E model as an open-source package for the R Statistical Programming Environment</p> <p>StrathE2E2 has two linked parts - a fishing fleet model and an ecology model. The fishing model represents catching, discarding and seabed disturbance rates by a range of gears and passes the results into the ecology model. The ecology model is a network of coupled ordinary differential equations representing the rates of change in nitrogen mass of organic detritus, dissolved inorganic nutrient and coarse guilds of living biomass spanning microbes to megafauna. The equations include representations of feeding, metabolism, reproduction, active migrations, advection and mixing. Environmental driving data include temperature, irradiance, hydrodynamics and nutrient inputs from rivers, atmosphere and ocean boundaries. The R-package includes functions for parameter optimization, global sensitivity analysis and Monte Carlo estimation of credible intervals for model outputs.</p>				<p>Within StrathE2E, as in real marine ecosystems, everything is directly or indirectly connected to everything else. The model simulates the fluxes of nutrient (nitrogen) through the ecosystem from dissolved inorganic (nitrate and ammonia), through living plankton, benthos and fish, to birds, seals and whales, and to fisheries. It also represents the return flows to dissolved nutrient through excretion and mineralization of detritus in the water column and sediment, and the physical oceanographic, land-sea, and air-sea exchanges across the geographic boundaries. The model incorporates mathematical function describing each predator-prey couplet in the food web, and density dependent mortality controls. External inputs include sea surface irradiance, temperature, hydrodynamic fluxes, freshwater input, river and atmospheric nitrate and ammonia inputs, ocean boundary nitrate, ammonia and suspended particulate concentrations, and fishery harvesting rates of shellfish, pelagic and demersal fish. Outputs from the model include time-series of the nitrogen mass of all state variables components, fluxes between components due to e.g. feeding, excretion, and exports to the ocean, atmosphere and to fishery landings.</p> <p>(see https://www.strath.ac.uk/science/mathematicsstatistics/smart/marineresourcmodelling/researchtools/strathe2e/)</p>			

FACTS AT A GLANCE

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KEYWORDS

Computer Simulation Model,
Global Sensitivity Analysis,
Monte Carlo Estimation,
Fishing Fleet Model,
Ecology Model,

LINKS TO RELATED PROJECTS

MISSION ATLANTIC Tools
<https://missionatlantic.eu/tools/>

LINKS TO RELATED WORK

STRATE2E-web-app site:
<https://rshiny.science.strath.ac.uk/apps/StrathE2EApp/>

REFERENCE

Heath MR et al (2021) StrathE2E2: An r package for modelling the dynamics of marine food webs and fisheries. *Methods Ecol Evol.* 2021; 12: 280–287. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13510>

TECHNOLOGY READINESS LEVEL

TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment

BACKGROUND

“The effects of anthropogenic or natural pressures applied to any part of an ecosystem are eventually felt everywhere to some extent through the phenomenon known as a ‘trophic cascade’ (Pace et al., 1999). Cascading effects are attenuated or amplified as they propagate through the food web, depending on the nature of the pressure and details of the ecology (Heath et al., 2014). Diagnosing the type and magnitude of pressures that an ecosystem can sustain before being fundamentally altered requires simulation with mathematical models that aim to represent the key ecological components and processes which govern cascades.”

[StrathE2E2: An r package for modelling the dynamics of marine food webs and fisheries - Heath - 2021 - Methods in Ecology and Evolution - Wiley Online Library](#)

StrathE2E simplifies these complex ecology and space parameters to be accessible. This is achieved through three unique, advanced characteristics of the web-app by means of its underlying models:

1. Speed, 2. Versatility, 3. Adaptability

This way, StrathE2E can run “what if” experiments and explore uncertainty, while comparing the outcome to real-world observation, to ensure sensibility.

APPLICATION

StrathE2E can simulate the effects of up to 12 different fishing fleets, returning landings, bycatch, discard, and seabed abrasion. Inputs are environmental data (light, temperature, nutrients, currents, sediments, rivers, atmosphere) and fishing rates (activity, selectivity, discarding, abrasion). The model then returns changes in the masses of 26 guilds over time. Every implementation has a habitat map and a set of input data. The map relates the real world to StrathE2E’s simplified data-structure. This is used to assemble input data from many sources, for a reference time period. Climate and other predictions can be used for time-periods in the future. The StrathE2E model, web-app and the R statistical environment are ready for use open source. Therefore, it can be deemed at TRL9. The next steps are focused on fostering uptake and application. The model is classed as being of intermediate complexity in terms of spatial and taxonomic resolution in order to permit the use of global sensitivity analysis and formal optimisation procedures to fit the model to an assemblage of observed data. The model is designed to explore trophic cascades in the marine ecosystem, in particular the propagation of effects of harvesting and river nutrient inputs through the food web, under oceanographic and temperature climate scenarios. The model has been intensively analysed for the North Sea and is currently being configured for a range of Atlantic shelf sea regions from southern Africa to the Arctic, taking driving data from NEMO-ERSEM model outputs. The model is available as a package for the R statistical environment. (see [StrathE2E | University of Strathclyde](#))

RELATION TO MISSION ‘RESTORE OUR OCEAN AND WATERS’: The unique speed, versatility and adaptability allow diverse applications in fisheries, as well as for monitoring planning and informed policy making. Due to its holistic approach, StrathE2E contributes to all three EU Mission Objectives, as well as to both enables, the ‘Digital Ocean and Water Knowledge System, known as Digital Twin of the Ocean’ and ‘Public mobilisation and engagement’.